

SECTION OF CHEMICAL SCIENCES

EVALUATION OF FRUIT RAW MATERIALS FOR THE PRODUCTION OF STRUCTURED SNACKS

Sleagun G.,

ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5543-8056>

Doctor of Technical Sciences

Scientific and Practical Institute of Horticulture,

Viticulture and Food Technologies in Chisinau,

Republic of Moldova, coordinating scientific researcher

Iushan L.

ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4028-221X>

Doctor of Technical Sciences

Scientific and Practical Institute of Horticulture,

Viticulture and Food Technologies in Chisinau,

Republic of Moldova, chief of laboratory

ABSTRACT

The article presents an analysis of the results of experimental research on the structuring of fruit puree with different content of insoluble dry substances. The structuring was carried out in the process of dehydration of the puree to different values of the water activity, ranging from 0.38-0.78.

The correlations between the water activity (*aw*) and the humidity of the studied products of different quality were established and also between the *aw* value and the content of insoluble dry substances.

The correlations between the values of the organoleptic assessment of the quality of structured purees and the activity of water, the content of dry substances insoluble in water (*Inap*) and dry substances insoluble in alcohol (*Inal*) are presented graphically. The most favorable intervals *aw*, *Inap*, *Inal* for the structuring of fruit purees were determined.

Keywords: fruit snacks, structuring of fruit puree, correlation activity of water – humidity, dry substances insoluble in water, dry substances insoluble in alcohol.

Introduction

Structured confectionery products such as marmalade, marshmallows are very popular among customers, as they are associated with a healthy diet through to the presence of a fruit component.

A specificity of fruit and berry types of these products is that they are made on the basis of gelling fruit and berry puree, mainly apple, and the structuring agent is the pectin contained in this puree.

The formation of a jelly structure in pectin solutions occurs as a result of the interaction of pectin molecules and depends on the molecular weight and features of its structure. In addition, the gelation process is affected by temperature, active acidity, mineral composition of the medium, and the type of dehydrating substances (sugars) [1]. Because gelation of pectin requires certain conditions, a number of requirements are imposed on fruit raw materials. The main objective indicator characterizing the technological properties of puree quality is the content of pectin substances and their gelling ability. However, fruit raw materials often do not have the necessary gelling ability due to the low content of pectin [2].

Pectin substances and their ability to structure are highly susceptible to changes depending on the type and varietal characteristics of fruits, their degree of maturity, keeping quality, conditions of storage and duration, and processing technology [3]. These factors lead to a shortage of raw materials with suitable characteristics for the preparation of structured fruit products, make the selection of raw materials an urgent problem,

taking into account the complexity of controlling the content of pectin substances.

This paper discusses structured fruit snacks, which are natural dried products of processing of fruit raw materials (pulp, paste, juice), obtained, in contrast to the above confectionery products, without added sugar [4]. The latter circumstance causes an additional requirement for the quality of fruit raw materials intended for obtaining structured snacks, namely the sugar content, which will provide the gelling process.

The objective of this work is to study the features of the chemical composition of fruit raw materials and the choice of objective indicators that characterize the technological properties of raw materials in terms of its use in the production of structured snacks.

Materials and methods

To solve the problem, the method of studying and analyzing the chemical composition of fruit raw materials was used, using reference data on the nutritional and energy value of food products [5,6], as well as other published research results on this issue.

Fresh fruits and berries and products of their processing, typical for the Republic of Moldova, were considered as fruit raw materials.

The content of the following main nutrients was analyzed: water, proteins, fats, carbohydrates, including mono- and disaccharides, non-starch polysaccharides, as well as soluble and insoluble substances, dietary fiber and their components.

For comparability of data on the content of individual nutrients of the chemical composition of fruit

raw materials, their content was recalculated for dry residue.

For the statistical evaluation of the analyzed data, the coefficient of variation ($CV, \%$) was used, determined by the formula: $CV=100\sigma/\bar{x}$,

where: σ - is the standard deviation, \bar{x} - is the average value of the indicator under study.

Results and discussions

Analysis of data on the content of main nutrients in fruit raw materials, presented as average values for certain groups: fresh pome fruits (apples, pears, quinces); fresh stone fruits (plums, apricots, peaches); fresh berries (aronia, blackberries, strawberries, grapes); fruits and berries processing products (peeled canned slices and pieces, puree, pulp, juice), led to the following conclusions:

- a characteristic feature of fresh fruits is a high water content of 80-91% and a wide variety of chemical composition;

- the amount of proteins in terms of dry matter averages 2.95% for pome fruits, 1.5-2.2 % for stone fruits; 7.2-11.7 % for berries and 3.0% for grapes;

- the amount of fat in terms of dry matter averages 5.1% for pome fruits, 5.9% for stone fruits; 0.5-4.1 % for berries and 1.0% for grapes. The relatively high content of protein and fat in the berries is due to the presence of small seeds in the berries, which are not separated during the analysis. The fat content of fruits and grapes is mainly due to the waxy coating on fresh fruits, which is largely removed during processing;

- in the dry residue, pome fruits contain approximately 83% carbohydrates, of which 62% are mono- and disaccharides and 17% are non-starchy polysaccharides (PNa); stone fruits contain approximately 82% carbohydrates, of which 72% are mono- and disaccharides and 11% PNa; grapes contain 83% carbohydrates, of which 77% are sugars and 3% are PNa. Thus, all three groups of fruits are similar in terms of the content of total carbohydrates (in terms of dry matter), the share of mono- and disaccharides increases, and the share of

PNa decreases in the series: pome fruits → stone fruits → grapes. Such berries as blackberries, strawberries are also characterized by a high content of total carbohydrates of 77-86%, however, they also contain a high percentage of PNa (20-40% abs.), the source of which, apparently, is the seeds of berries;

- fruit processing products obtained by cleaning, rubbing, pressing have a reduced amount of insoluble polysaccharides, fats and proteins. The fruit skin differs from the fruit pulp in having a lower water and sugar content, but a higher content of protopectin and fiber.

The composition of fresh fruits and products of their processing is shown schematically in Fig.1.

When compilation the scheme, the classification of carbohydrates presented in the report of the World Health Organization [7] was used.

Using the published data on the content of water-soluble and insoluble substances [8], we obtained their values expressed in terms of the total amount of dry substances, and carried out a statistical evaluation of the obtained data. To compare the degree of dispersion of the given data (Table 1) in relation to their average, the coefficients of variation were calculated for a joint sample of pome and stone fruits, as well as berries. As it turned out, the results of the determination of insoluble and soluble substances in fruits are characterized by a significant difference in the coefficients of variation, almost 4 times.

Thus, the indicator of the content of insoluble substances in fruits compared to the content of soluble substances is more informative and to a greater extent reflects the differences in the chemical composition of different types of fruits. For berries, data relating to the absolute contents of insoluble and soluble substances have the same CV values (35-36%), while data relating to the proportion of insoluble substances have a lower CV value (21%). Apparently, such a difference between fruits and berries is due to the fact that berries were analyzed together with seeds.

Fig.1. Composition of fresh fruits and products of their processing

Table 1.

The content of insoluble and soluble dry substances in fruits and berries, g/100 g dry matter

Indicator	Apples	Pears	Quince	Apricot	Peach	Plum	Cherry	Sweet cherry
Dry substances insoluble, %	3,03	5,24	6,42	2,65	3,00	2,17	2,08	2,15
Dry substances soluble,%	15,53	15,43	12,46	11,50	14,21	14,29	15,19	16,98
Percentage of dry substances insoluble, %	16,33	25,35	34,04	18,73	17,43	13,18	12,04	11,24
	Rowan	Gooseberry	Raspberry	Red currant	Black currant	Lingonberry/ Cranberry	Strawberry	Blackberry
Dry substances insoluble, %	8,11	4,65	5,98	6,35	8,02	4,20/4,40	1,90	6,19
Dry substances soluble,%	19,46	9,65	9,42	9,05	14,65	13,24/7,6	7,00	10,18
Percentage of dry substances insoluble, %	29,42	32,91	38,83	41,23	35,38	24,1/36,6	24,35	37,81

Chemical composition indicators taken from reference tables [9] and related to the content of sugars (mono- and disaccharides) and polysaccharides for a wide range of fruits and berries were converted to dry matter and estimated by their spread around the average using the coefficient of variation. The results presented

in Table 2 and illustrated in Figure 2 show that the sugar content has small differences ($CV=8.6\%$) within the range of fruits and average in berries ($CV=21\%$); the content of polysaccharides, both individual species and their sum, are characterized by higher CV values from 30.5 to 47.5%.

Table 2.

The content of sugars and polysaccharides in fruits and berries, g/100g dry matter

Fruits and berries	Indicator						
	Sum of sugars	Polysaccharides				Sum of polysaccharides	PNa
		Cellulose	Hemicelluloses	Pectin	Starch		
Apricot	71,4	5,7	2,1	5,0	0	12,8	12,8
Cherry	68,7	3,3	0,67	2,7	0	6,67	6,67
Sweet cherry	75,3	2,1	1,4	2,9	0	6,4	6,4
Plum	88,5	3,8	1,5	6,9	0,77	12,97	12,2
Peach	67,9	6,4	1,4	5,0	0	12,8	12,8
Apples	76,9	4,6	3,1	7,7	6,2	21,6	15,4
Pears	73,3	4,0	1,3	4,0	3,3	13,3	9,3
Grapes	75,8	3,0	3,0	3,0	0	9,0	9,0
Strawberry	39,6	25,8	1,3	4,5	0,65	32,25	31,6
Gooseberry	53,5	11,8	1,2	4,1	0	17,1	17,1
Raspberry	46,2	28,3	0,56	3,3	-	32,16	32,16
Sea buckthorn	29,5	27,6	0,59	2,35	-	30,54	30,54
Black currant	44,7	20,0	0,67	7,3	4,0	31,97	27,97

Fig.2. Coefficient of variation in the content of sugars and polysaccharides in fruits and berries

Numerous studies consider changes in the chemical composition of fruits in the process of their development and ripening. Thus, during the ripening of apples of the Jonathan variety, it was found that the total sugar content increases, and the content of dry substances insoluble in alcohol (pentosans hydrolyzed by acid, hemicelluloses, cellulose, starch, etc.) decreases, respectively, characterized by $CV=9.5\%$ and $CV=38.7\%$.

As plums ripen, total sugar rises steadily, with CV values ranging from 18.5% (Hungarian) to 34% (Renclod). In variety type Hungarian, the content of dry substances soluble changes little ($CV=18.5$), while the content of dry substances insoluble in alcohol decreases markedly ($CV=36.8$). During the development of the Renklod fruit, the amount of pectin increases and then decreases significantly as it ripens ($CV=52.0\%$).

Published research data on changes in the chemical composition of apples during their refrigerated storage demonstrate a (10-20)-fold decrease in acidity over

two years of storage of apples (KA 1.7-1.2 times in a controlled atmosphere), slight changes in total sugar and (2.2-2.3) fold loss of pectin substances (in AC by 1.5 times). These changes are accompanied by a decrease in fruit hardness by 3.0-3.6 times (in AC by 1.3-1.7 times).

It is important to note that the components of the chemical composition have certain technological properties and the variability of the chemical composition leads to a change in these properties. So, the proteins that make up nitrogenous substances are in colloidal form, most of them are insoluble in water, some are soluble in 50-90% alcohol. Free aminoacids are soluble in water, only proline is soluble in alcohol. Mono- and disaccharides, polyols are easily soluble in water and in alcohol of 70% concentration. Free organic acids, depending on the salts formed, are characterized by different dissolution abilities in cold and hot water and alcohol. The amount of starch increases during fruit development, decreases during

ripening (more than 7 times for apples) and disappears during storage. In water, depending on the temperature of the solution and structural features, starch is able to dissolve or form pastes, interaction with alcohol is determined by the concentration of alcohol solutions.

Pectins include:

a) free pectin dissolved in fruit juice;

b) pectin formed as a result of hydrolysis of protopectin and protopectin-a compound of pectin with cellulose of cell walls. With maturation, the amount of pectin decreases, and the number of methoxyl groups in pectin increases, which means that the rate of gelation and the strength of the jelly increase. During fruit ripening, hydrolysis of protopectin occurs. Overripe fruits do not form jelly and not to have protopectin, which causes the rigidity of unripe fruits.

Free pectin can be extracted from plant tissue with cold water. When dissolved in water, it forms a colloidal solution, precipitated by alcohol. Boiling in an acidic environment leads to the breakdown of pectin. Protopectin is insoluble in water, alcohol, ether. When cooked in water (starting from 80°C), it becomes soluble (pectin) as a result of hydrolysis, which determines the digestibility of the fruit. The resulting pectin contains araban (alcohol-soluble fraction) and pectin acid.

The walls of young fruit cells are composed of cellulose and hemicelluloses. With age, non-carbohydrate insoluble substances, lignin and cutin, are formed in the cell walls. Hemicelluloses are easily hydrolyzed under the influence of weak acid solutions, forming pentosans and hexosans. Pentosans are soluble in water, give sticky solutions, precipitate from them with alcohol.

As follows from the above data, dry substances insoluble in alcohol may include some nitrogenous substances, some acid salts, starch and certain types of dextrans, pentosans, cellulose, lignin, cutin, protopectin and pectin.

Conclusions

Selected and summarized information regarding the chemical composition, as well as some of the changes that occur during ripening, storage and processing of fruits of various types and varieties.

A higher variability in the content of dry substances insoluble was revealed in comparison with the content of dry substances soluble (sugars, etc.).

It has been suggested that it is possible to use indicators of the content of dry substances insoluble in water and dry substances insoluble in alcohol to

evaluate fruit raw materials intended for obtaining structured fruit snacks.

References

1. ОБОЛКИНА, В.И.; КРАПИВНИЦКАЯ, И.А.; ЙОВБАК, У.С. и др. Использование пектинов и пектинсодержащих продуктов при производстве кондитерских изделий с желеобразной структурой // Продукты и ингредиенты. 2013. №2. С. 10–12. [cit. 07.02.2022]. Disponibil la: <http://dspace.nuft.edu.ua/jspui/bitstream/123456789/6862/1/oviipppppkigs.pdf>
2. ДЖАМИЛЯ, Р.С.; ДЖАБОВА, А.С.; ШАОВА Л.Г. и др. Содержание пектинов в различных видах плодовых культур и их физико-химические свойства. // Вестник ВГУИТ. 2016. №2. С. 170–174. [cit. 07.02.2022]: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/soderzhanie-pektinov-v-razlichnyh-vidah-plodovyh-kultur-i-ih-fiziko-himicheskie-svoystva/viewer>
3. ŞLEAGUN G. Particularitățile tehnologice ale materiei prime de fructe și legume ca obiect de uscare. IE. Chișinău, 2002, 28p
4. ŞLEAGUN G., PAVLINCUIUC M. Clasificarea snack-urilor de fructe în baza studiului diversității lor pe piața mondială. În *Intellectus*, 3-4/ 2019, p.77-85
5. Agricultural Research Service. FoodData Central. USDA <https://fdc.nal.usda.gov/>
6. Химический состав пищевых продуктов: Книга 1: Справочные таблицы содержания основных пищевых веществ и энергетической ценности пищевых продуктов/Под редакцией проф. И.М. Скурихина-2 изд., перераб. и доп.-Москва.: ВО «Агропромиздат», 1987.-224 с.
7. FAO/WHO. 1998. Carbohydrates in Human Nutrition: Report of a Joint FAO/WHO Expert Consultation, 14-18 April 1997, Rome. FAO Food and Nutrition Paper No. 66. Rome. [access 11.02.2022]. Disponibil la: <https://www.fao.org/3/x2650t/x2650t02.htm>
8. БУРОВА Т.Е. Основы технологии пищевых продуктов. Лабораторный практикум. Учебно-методическое пособие. С.-П. 2014. с.53 [access 11.02.2022]. Disponibil la: <https://books.ifmo.ru/file/pdf/1579.pdf>
9. Химический состав пищевых продуктов. Кн.2: Справочные таблицы содержания аминокислот, жирных кислот, витаминов, макро- и микро-элементов, органических кислот и углеводов/Под ред. проф., д-ра техн. наук И.М. Скурихина и проф., д-ра мед. наук М.Н. Волгарева, - 2-е изд., перераб. и доп.-М.: Агропромиздат, 1987.-360 с.